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БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ
ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ | JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE**ORZIKULOV Azam Orzikulovich**
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**ANTIVIRAL THERAPY IN VIRAL HEPATITIS “C” DISEASE EFFICIENCY
(A CASE FROM PRACTICE)**

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 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15007891>**ABSTRACT**

Viral hepatitis C is a disease that causes serious health problems all over the world. The lack of specific prevention of chronic viral hepatitis C is an important medical and social problem in connection with the development of cirrhosis of the liver, based on the fact that at the initial stage the clinical signs are nonspecific. The guidelines and standards recommended for use in the treatment of chronic viral hepatitis C indicate that the main goal of therapy is the long-term suppression of viral replication. The article mentions that in clinical practice, in the case of "Chronic viral hepatitis C", the administration of the antiviral drug Ledvir (sofosbuvir 400 mg + ledispavir 90 mg) for a short period during clinical and laboratory monitoring leads to a positive change in clinical and laboratory signs, in the long term – to prolonged suppression of virus replication.

Keywords: hepatitis C virus, viral replication, HCV genotype, genotype 1B

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**ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ПРОТИВОВИРУСНОЙ ТЕРАПИИ ПРИ ВИРУСНОМ
ГЕПАТИТЕ “С” (СЛУЧАЙ ИЗ ПРАКТИКИ)****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Вирусный гепатит С - это заболевание, которое вызывает серьезные проблемы со здоровьем во всем мире. Отсутствие специфической профилактики хронического вирусного гепатита С является важной медицинской и социальной проблемой в связи развитием цирроза печени, основанного на том факте, что на начальной стадии клинические признаки неспецифичны. Указания и стандарты, рекомендуемые для применения в практике лечения хронического

вирусного гепатита С, указывают на то, что основной целью терапии является долгосрочное подавление репликации вируса. В статье упоминается, что в клинической практике в случае "Хронического вирусного гепатита С" назначение противовирусного препарата "Ледвир" (софосбувир 400 мг+ ледиспавир 90 мг) на короткий период при клинико-лабораторном мониторинге приводит к положительному изменению клинико-лабораторных признаков, в долгосрочной перспективе – к длительному подавлению репликации вируса.

Ключевые слова: вирус гепатита С, вирусная репликация, генотип HCV, генотип 1В

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VIRUSLI GEPATIT "S" KASALLIGIDA VIRUSGA QARSHI DAVO SAMARADORLIGI (AMALIYOTDAN BIR HOLAT)

ANNOTATSIYA

Virusli gepatit S butun dunyoda sog'liqqa jiddiy muammo tug'diruvchi kasallik hisoblanadi. Surunkali virusli gepatit C kasalligining o'ziga xos profilaktikasining yo'qligi, boshlang'ich bosqichida klinik belgilar nospesifik bo'lganligi va jigar sirrozining rivojlanishi tufayli muhim tibbiy va ijtimoiy muammodir. Surunkali virusli gepatit S kasalligini davolash uchun amaliyotga tavsiya qilingan yo'riqnoma va standartlarda virus replikatsiyasini uzoq muddatli bostirish terapiyaning asosiy maqsadi ekanligi ko'rsatilgan. Maqolada klinik amaliyotda "Surunkali virusli gepatit S" kasalligida klinik va laboratoriya monitoring kuzatuv bilan qisqa muddat davomida "Ledvir" (sofosbuvir 400 mg+ ledispavir 90 mg) virusga qarshi dori vositasi buyurilishi klinik laborator belgilarning ijobiy tomonga o'zgarishiga, virus replikatsiyasining uzoq muddat davomida bostirilishiga olib kelishi aytib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: gepatit S virusi, virus replikatsiyasi, HCV genotipi, 1b genotip

Mavzu dolzarbligi: Surunkali virusli gepatit C kasalligi aholi ning tarqalishi, infeksiyaning yuqori chastotasi va uzoq yillar davomida jigar sirrozi shakllanishi bois, ustuvor muammo sifatida zamonaviy tibbiyotning dolzarb nuqtasi hisoblanadi. Surunkali virusli gepatit S kasalligini davolash uchun amaliyotga tavsiya qilingan yo'riqnoma va standartlarda virus replikatsiyasini uzoq muddatli bostirish terapiyaning asosiy maqsadi ekanligi ko'rsatilgan.

Hozirgi vaqtda surunkali gepatit C kasalligi mehnatga layoqatli aholi orasida keng tarqalganligi, ko'pincha asoratlanishi va ayrim hollarda noxush oqibatlar kuzatilishi bois, davlatga tibbiy-ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy zarar keltirishi bois, dolzarb muammo hisoblanadi. JSST ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, Rossiya aholisining taxminan 3% gepatit C virusi bilan kasallangan. O'tkazilgan tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, AQSHda HCV infeksiyasi bo'lgan bemorlarning 25% jigar sirroziga chalingan, yaqin yillar ichida ularning soni 37% gacha oshishi kuzatilmoqda [1,2,3].

Surunkali gepatit C kasalligining jigar gepatotsellyulyar karsinomasiga va jigar sirroziga o'tishining oldini olishda yagona usul virusga qarshi terapiya hisoblanadi. Rossiyalik mutaxassislar tavsiyasiga ko'ra, surunkali gepatit C bilan kasallangan bioximik o'zgarishlarga bog'liq bo'lmagan holda barcha bemorlar, jigar sirrozi bilan kasallangan kompensatsiya bosqichidagi bemorlar virusga qarshi terapiya qabul qilishlari lozim. Mutaxassislar fikriga ko'ra, virusga qarshi terapiya jigar to'qimasidagi morfologik o'zgarishlar darajasiga qarab belgilanadi: (fibroz bosqichiga bog'liq): yaqqol ifodalangan fibroz (METAVIR F3 - F4) virusga qarshi terapiya darhol boshlanishi ko'rsatilgan, o'rtacha ifodalangan fibrozda (METAVIR F2) virusga qarshi terapiyani boshlash maqsadga muvofiq hisoblanadi, kam ifodalangan fibrozda (METAVIR F1) virusga qarshi terapiya uchun ko'rsatmalar individual aniqlanadi [8]. Surunkali virusli gepatit C kasalligi etiologiyasiga, genotipiga, patologik jarayonning bosqichiga (jigar fibrozi yoki jigar sirrozi bosqichi), bemorning yoshi, bir vaqtning o'zida mavjud hamroh kasalliklari va boshqa ko'plab omillarga bog'liq ko'p

davolash rejimlari mavjud. Shunga bog‘liq tavsiya etilgan virusga qarshi terapiya sxemasi samaradorligi belgilanadi [6]. Oxirgi yillarda viruslar kinetikasini erta o‘rganish surunkali virusli gepatitlar terapevtik paradigmasida o‘zgarishlarga olib keldi: surunkali virusli gepatit C 1 va 4 genotiplari bilan kasallangan bemorlar kasallikning 2 yoki 3 genotiplari bilan kasallangan bemorlarga nisbatan uzoqroq davolanishlari kerak. Tadqiqotlarda ma‘lum bo‘lishicha, viremiyaning pasayish tezligi terapiyaning dastlabki 12 haftasida hatto virusning genotipiga qaraganda terapiya samaradorligining muhim prognostik omili bo‘lib hisoblanadi. Virusga qarshi terapiya “genotipga qarab” emas, balki “javobga qarab” terapiya bilan almashtirildi [5].

Hozirgi vaqtda 99% hollarda virusga qarshi terapiya paytida barqaror virusologik javobga erishish virusni to‘liq yo‘q qilish imkoniyati bilan bog‘liqligi va virusga qarshi terapiyaning so‘nggi nuqtasi ekanligi isbotlangan [7]. Tez virusologik javob (TVJ) davolashning 4-hafta oxirida qon zardobidagi surunkali virusli gepatit RNK darajasining PZR usulining sezgirlik chegarasidan past bo‘lgan qiymatlarga pasayishini anglatadi (qoida tariqasida, 15-50 ME/ml dan kam). “Erta virusologik javob” atamasi virusga qarshi dorilar bilan davolashning 12-haftasida boshlang‘ich darajaga nisbatan virus yuklamasining 100-marta yoki undan ko‘p ($\geq 2 \log 10$) kamayganligini ko‘rsatadi. “Sekin virusologik javob” (SVJ) - bu davolashning 12-haftasida boshlang‘ich darajaga (to‘liq bo‘lmagan EVJ) nisbatan virus yuklamasining 100-marta yoki undan ko‘p ($\geq 2 \log 10$) kamayishi va 24-haftaga kelib uning to‘liq yo‘qolishi [4, 9] hisoblanadi. Shunday qilib, HCV infeksiyasi 99% bemorlarda virusga qarshi terapiya kursini tugatgandan so‘ng barqaror virusologik javob shakllangach, davolangan hisoblanadi [2,11], agar bemorning tanasida davolash kursi tugaganidan HCV infeksiyasi (RNK virus yuklamasi) 12 (TVJ -12) yoki 24 (SVJ-24) haftadan so‘ng aniqlanilmasa, terapevtik samaradorlikka erishilgan hisoblanadi [10]. Virus eliminatsiyasini bartaraf etishga va barqaror virusologik javobga erishishga hissa qo‘shadigan bemor organizmining individual xususiyatlari orasida quyidagilar mavjud: yevropoid irqqa mansublik, bemor yoshi, past tana massasi indeksi, alkogol yoki giyohvandlikka qaramlik yo‘qligi, ruhiy kasallik, insulin rezistentlik yo‘qligi, steatoz va jigar fibrozi aniqlanilmasligi. Bemorning motivatsiyasi va uning davolanishga mas‘uliyati ham katta ahamiyatga ega [9].

Tadqiqot maqsadi: virusli gepatit S kasalligida virusga qarshi terapiya samaradorligini amaliyotda baholash.

Tekshiruv usullari va materiallari: Shu maksadda biz “Surunkali virusli gepatit C” bilan xastalangan bir bemorning ambulator kasallik tarixini retrospektiv va perspektiv tahlil etdik. Bemorda epidemiologik, klinik, laborator tekshiruvlar o‘tkazildi.

Tadqiqot muhokamasi: Bemor K. J. 20 yoshda, Samarqand viloyati Kattaqo‘rg‘on tumanidan murojaat etgan. 25.05.2018 yilda Samarqand viloyati yuqumli kasalliklar klinik shifoxonasiga (VYUKKSH) umumiy holsizlik, ishtahaning pasayishi, qorni damlashidan, o‘ng qovurg‘a yoyidagi va qorin soxasidagi og‘riqqa, og‘riqning orqa kurak va bel sohasi bo‘ylab tarqalishiga, darmonsizligidan, charchoq bo‘lishiga, ishtahasizlik, behollikka, ko‘ngli aynib turishga, buyrak sohasidagi og‘riqlar, charchoq, ko‘ngil aynishi, burun qonashi shikoyatlari bilan murojaat etdi. Anamnezidan bemor 18.05.2017 yilda tishlarini davolatgan. Bir yil davomida bemorni hech narsa bezovta qilmaganligi bois, hech kimga murojaat etmagan. 24.05.2018 kuni yuqoridagi klinik belgilar kuchayib borganligi sababli 25.05.2018 yili tuman shifoxonasiga murojaat etgan. Tuman shifoxonasidan VYUKKSH shifoxonasiga yuborilgan.

Ob‘ektiv ko‘rikda: Vazni 49 kg. Umumiy axvoli o‘rtacha og‘ir, es-xushi ravshan. Darmonsiz, kamquvvat, lanjlik bor. Ko‘z sklerasi va terisida sariqlik yo‘q. Terisi yuzasida dog‘lar aniqlanadi, toshmalar kuzatilmaydi. Teri osti yog‘ qatlami o‘rtacha rivojlangan, tana tuzilishi asteniklarga xos. Mushaklar tonusi saqlangan. Nafas olishi erkin burun orqali, yordamchi mushaklar ishtirok etmaydi. 1 daq 16 ta. Auskultatsiyada o‘pkasida dag‘al nafas eshitiladi. Auskultatsiyada yurak tonlari bo‘g‘iqlashgan. Funktsional shovqinlar eshitilmaydi. YUKS-minutiga 62 ta. Puls ritmik o‘rtacha to‘liqlik va taranglikda. AQB 90/60 mm. sim.ust.ga teng. Ishtahasi pasaygan, doim ko‘ngil aynishi bo‘ladi, qusmagan. Lablari nam. Tili nam, oq karash bilan qoplangan. Qorni yumshoq. biroz dam. Bemor qabziyatga moyil. Jigar o‘lchamlari qovurg‘a ravog‘idan: L.parsternalis +3,0; L.medioclavicularis +3,0; L.axillaris ant +3,0 paypaslanadi. Talog‘i paypaslanmaydi. Qorni yumshoq

yengil dam, simmetrik, palpatsiyada og‘riq o‘t qopi va epigastriya sohasida. Og‘riq orqa kurak va bel sohasiga uzatiladi. Ichaklar peristaltikasi saqlangan. Axlati davriyligi buzilgan. Buyrak sohasida ko‘zga ko‘rinarli o‘zgarishlar kuzatilmaydi. Pasternaskiy simptomi ikki tomonlama musbat. Siydik rangi to‘qlashgan, miqdori normal. Bemor juda passiv. Kayfiyati tushkun. Savollarga istamay javob qaytaradi. Ko‘p gap yoqmaydi. Ko‘pincha yolg‘iz qolishni istaydi.

Lab. ma‘lumotlar: gemoglobin -104,0 g/l, eritr-2,18/1*10X12, leyk-6,72*10X9, metamielotsitlar-4, EChT-8 mm/soat. Tromb-163,0

Suxarev bo‘yicha qon ivish vaqti: Bosh: 4 daq 41 lahza. Tugal: 5 daq 08 lahza.

Qon biokimyoviy tah: umumiy bil: 51,6 mk/mol Bog‘langan bil-40,6; Bog‘lanmagan bil-11,0; AST-1,50; ALT-2,50; Timol sinamasi-8,56; Sulema sinamasi -0,80;

Fibroskan tekshiruvda F0 (8,0 kRA) qayd etildi.

IFT: HCV musbat ekanligi aniqlanildi.

PZR tekshiruvda 1,72 ME+07 HCV*ml ekanligi ma‘lum bo‘ldi. HCV genotipi bo‘yicha PZR tekshiruvda 1b genotip aniqlanildi. O‘tkazilgan tadqiqotlarga ko‘ra, O‘zbekiston hududida asosan 1b genotip nisbatan ko‘p uchrashi ko‘rsatib o‘tilgan [5,6].

27.08.2017 yil 542 sonli “O‘zbekiston respublikasida virusli gepatitlarning tashxisoti davosi va profilaktikasi bo‘yicha chora tadbirlarni yanada takomillashtirish to‘g‘risida” buyrug‘iga asosan bemorda tekshiruvlar o‘tkazilgan va yakuniy tashxis qo‘yilgan. Surunkali gepatit C tashxisi virusologik status (genotip va virusli yuklama), jarayon faolligi (biokimyoviy yoki gistologik), shuningdek kasallik bosqichiga qarab aniqlangan (elastografi yoki morfologik tekshiruvlarga asosan). Shuningdek, surunkali gepatit C tashxisini qo‘yishda asosiy omil jarayonning muddatiga bog‘liq (6 oydan ziyod bo‘lishi kerak). Surunkali gepatit S da jigardan tashqari kuzatiladigan quyidagi o‘zgarishlar hisobga olinadi:

- depressiya;
- krioglobulinemiya;
- B-hujayraviy limfoproliferativ kasalliklar;
- kechki teri porfiriyasi;
- vaskulitlar;
- qizil yassi lishay;
- Shegren sindromi;
- glomerulonefrit;
- qandli diabet 2 tipa.

Kuzatuvimizda bemorda jigardan tashqari o‘zgarishlardan faqat depressiya qayd etilgan.

Surunkali gepatitlarda yallig‘lanish jarayoniga bog‘liq gepatitlar faolligi morfologik diagnostikasi quyidagi omillar yordamida baholandi (1-jadval).

Surunkali gepatitlarda jarayon faolligiga bog‘liq morfologik diagnostikasi

1-jadval.

№	Gistologik tashxis	METAVIR	Knodell (IV)	Ishak
1.	Surunkali gepatit minimal faollik darajasi	A1	0-3	0-3
2.	Surunkali gepatit past faollik darajasi	A1	4-5	4-6
3.	Surunkali gepatit o‘rta faollik darajasi	A2	6-9	7-9
4.	Surunkali gepatit yuqori faollik darajasi	A3	10-12	10-15
5.	Surunkali gepatit yuqori faollik darajasi ko‘prikimon nekroz o‘choqlari bilan	AZ	13-18	16-18

Yuqoridagi jadvalga asosan bemorga quyidagi tashxis qo'yildi: Surunkali gepatit C. O'rta faollik darajasi. Replikatsiya davri (PZR tekshiruvda 1,72 ME+07 HCV*ml).

Bemorlarga virusga qarshi terapiya buyurilishiga ko'rsatmalar:

Surunkali gepatit C bilan kasallangan barcha bemorlar;

METAVIR bo'yicha F0-F1 fibroz darajasi kuzatilgan bemorlarni virusga qarshi terapiya individual tartibda belgilanadi.

METAVIR bo'yicha F2 fibroz darajasi kuzatilgan bemorlar rejali ravishda virusga qarshi terapiya qabul qilishlari lozim;

METAVIR bo'yicha F3-F4 fibroz darajasi kuzatilgan barcha bemorlar birinchi navbatda virusga qarshi terapiya qabul qilishlari kerak;

Quyidagi holatlarda virusga qarshi terapiya bemor ahvoriga qarab tayinlanadi:

-a'zolar transplantatsiyasidan so'ng;

jigardan tashqari o'zgarishlar: essensial aralash krioglobulinemiya 2 yoki 3 tipi alohida a'zolar shikastlanishi bilan (vaskulit va b.),

-kechki teri porfiriya.

Koinfeksiya HIV-1.

Koinfeksiya HBV.

Qandli diabet 2 tipi.

Surunkali gemodializdagi bemorlar;

HCV-infeksiyasi bilan infitsirlangan, homiladorlikni rejalashtirayotgan ayollar.

Bemorga tashxis asosida bir kurs ambulator davo muolajalaridan so'ng, 3 oy davomida "Ledvir" (sofosbuvir 400 mg+ ledispavir 90 mg) virusga qarshi dori vositasi buyurildi. Bemorda 3 oy davomida dori vositasining nojo'ya ta'siri aniqlanilmadi. 21.10.18 yil RNK HCV PZR tekshiruvda manfiy ekanligi aniqlanildi. Fibroskan tekshiruvda F0 (3,6 kRA) qayd etildi. 2018 yildan buyon doimiy ravishda dispanser kuzatuvda turadi. Dinamikada kuzatuv davomida bemorda klinik laborator o'zgarishlar kuzatilmadi.

Xulosa: Shunday qilib, klinik amaliyotda "Surunkali virusli gepatit C" kasalligida klinik va laboratoriya monitoring kuzatuv bilan qisqa muddat davomida "Ledvir" (sofosbuvir 400 mg+ ledispavir 90 mg) virusga qarshi dori vositasi buyurilishi klinik laborator belgilarning ijobiy tomonga o'zgarishiga, virus replikatsiyasining uzoq muddat davomida bostirilishiga olib keldi. Bemorlarda virusga qarshi dori vositasidan keyin yuzaga keladigan noxush holatlar deyarli qayd etilmadi. Bizning ma'lumotlarimiz adabiyotlardagi ma'lumotlar bilan mos tushadi [4,7,8]. Bu borada klinik tadqiqotlarni davom ettirish lozim.

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10 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

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